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SOVEREIGNTY AND SUBJECTION IN THE *SPRING SONATA*

M. K. Čiurlionis has been called a Symbolist, painting not representations of nature but creations of his imagination and dreams. But in the four paintings of the *Spring Sonata*, he just painted cliffs, trees, windmills, fish, and spires. The paintings are representational, not abstract. Čiurlionis often painted complex buildings and trees with much detail and precision, but here only the fish has a carefully drawn shape, has only one vague fin, and lacks eyes. These paintings are not really about things. Instead, they are about what the ancient Greeks and philosopher Emmanuel Levinas called the elements. The third painting is about water. The second is about the sky, the first is about bedrock exposed on a cliff wall and earth made by the action of water on rock, and the fourth painting is about outer space. M. K. Čiurlionis, in his paintings, is engaged not in things but in elements – water, sky, earth, and outer space. He is revealing different viewpoints and fascinating, pleasurable experiences of real things, doubling, reflecting one another, and with what lies beyond what we perceive. When we go to experience the landscape, we are not only lured by the shapes and colors of things. We experience a more profound fascination: the immersion in light, in water, in the substance of earth and rock. The captivating fact is that real things project shadows and reflections of themselves in water and mirages in the air and duplicate in other things like themselves, varying somewhat. The troubling and vulnerable sense is that the landscape where we live is also the land of death.

Keywords: M. K. Čiurlionis, *Spring Sonata*, elements, land of death, phenomenology of aesthetics.

Scherzo

M. K. Čiurlionis has been called a Symbolist, painting not representations of nature, but creations of his imagination and dreams. But in the four paintings of the *Spring Sonata*, he just painted cliffs, trees, windmills, fish, and spires. The paintings are representational, not abstract. Čiurlionis often painted complex buildings and trees with much detail and precision, but here only the fish has a carefully drawn shape and has only one vague fin and lacks eyes. These paintings are not really about things; instead, they are about what the ancient Greeks and philosopher

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Scherzo (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

Emmanuel Levinas called the elements; the third painting is about water; the second is about the sky; the first is about bedrock exposed on a cliff wall and earth made by the action of water on rock; the fourth painting is about outer space.

Let us begin with the third painting – Allegro.

The empty space, the minimal strokes, the absence of color, one featured animal off-center – these are characteristics of Chinese and Japanese painting.

This painting is composed mainly of water. Water symbolizes transparency, freedom of the gaze. It is visible only when things are reflected or duplicated on it such as: mountains, trees, or moving flakes of sunlight.

The painting shows a landscape, but not as seen from one viewpoint. Instead, what is seen in the painting is seen from different locations; what is seen directs the viewer to go to different vantage points.

The viewer is situated on the ground at some distance before a high stone wall with a gate. The gate could be the type that encloses the mansion of a rich landowner. But this wall encloses a large body of water.

The viewer is now situated above it, with a bird's eye view, the view is unobstructed and sweeps freely over a great distance. In the depth of the water, we see a row of buildings vaguely outlined, a dead mansion or town buried in the waters of the lake. The lake is enclosed in the far distance by a wall of mountains with clouds settled between them. They are reflected, duplicated, on the surface of the water below.

In the stone wall before us, to the right, there is an opening without a gate. The viewer passes through it and is at once in the water, facing a fish at eye level, very close, with two more fish at eye level, but further away.

The fish are sleek, elegant, and swift. Our eyes do not look at these fish, but rather join them as they dart through the water, allegro. But the fish are still, stopped by a net dropped across the water that extends into the sky in the top left of the picture. The net is held up by three large floaters that are shaped like slices of bread or of fruit, but are of the color and density of the rocks of the front wall. Rocks form the base that supports the ground and water over it, here the rocks hover just over the surface of the water. In the distance, there is a line of floaters that hold up a net that we don't see but is there.

We feel a tension between the freedom of our view over the vast unobstructed space and in the transparency of the water, and then the confinement of the fish on all sides which is barely visible.

When we go to the country for a walk to enjoy the landscape, there are two different ways to experience the landscape because there are two different positions of the viewer.

A tree, a rock formation, a mountain stream attracts us, and it directs us to the place that we must go to see it – up that path, around that bend, up on those boulders. We are directed, ordered by the tree, the rocks, and the stream, dependent on them, subjected to them. We have the pleasure of seeing a great many things, their different sides, and profiles, intimately, but it takes time and effort to get to the viewpoints to which we are directed.

When we go to see the country around us, we do look for a lookout point, the top of a hill or the edge of a cliff where a vast expanse is spread out before us, exposed to our view. Here we have the pleasure of seeing a great many things, each one in its place, and our view is unobstructed, dominating, freely sweeping across the whole landscape, sovereign, free to bring into focus anything we like. There is something godlike in that experience. But at the same time, the rocks, trees, and rivers appear interlocked with one another, not interacting with us, but remote and alien.

In the first experience, we are directed, commanded by the things; in the second viewpoint, we dominate the things.

Landscape painting especially in northern Europe was the most important art in the 19th century. The paintings showed wild and inaccessible places, ice-covered mountains, dense forests, stormy seas. The artist and the viewer situated at a height commanded and dominated the landscape, armed his sovereignty.

Čiurlionis's painting *Allegro* shows one landscape but not as seen or visible from a commanding vantage point. The things direct the viewer. To see this wall, you have to be on the ground some forty feet in front of it; to see this lake and the distant mountains, you have to see it from the air above like a bird; to see the fish you have to be in the water with them.

Andante

Let us turn to the second painting – *Andante*, slow movement. Again, we see a lake close to us, or a lake in the distance that we catch sight of between gaps in the hillocks. On top of them are six windmills. But no roads lead to them, and there are no fields of grain in the surrounding barren land. Their blades or vanes are huge; they hide from view the buildings that support them, and they almost scrape the ground as they turn. But they remain still, no wind turns them in this land of death. Their vanes are not of lightweight cedar sheets, but are massive and dense like lengths of timber, like the beams of the cross of Christ's crucifixion, multiplied on the Hill of Crosses near Šiauliai in northern Lithuania.

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Andante (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

The windmills are reflected, duplicated in the sky. Now the viewer is situated in the sky close to and at eye level of a windmill with another above it to the right, and eight windmills behind in the far distance. It is strange to see windmills, big heavy structures that must be securely anchored on the ground, in the sky, but on the other hand, the sky is the realm of winds. The windmills are set on hills of cloud that do not stop the vanes as they extend far beyond the base of the building and radiate like beams of pulsating light. The windmills reflect, as if duplicating the Sun.

Real things engender doubles of themselves. If there is a tree, it has a double like itself; if there is a stone, there are more stones like it. They cast shadows, they cast reflections of themselves on the surface of the water, they double as mirages in the air. Real shadows, real reflections, real as they are.

What we identify as figments of our imagination have no doubles. When we hear a cry of alarm in the night but there is no other cry heard, we realize that we did not really hear it, we only imagined it. If we see a snake on the floor of the library, we step back and do not see it again in another place, we know we only imagined it. A ghost casts no shadow and is not reflected in a mirror.

A double is not a duplicate; it is in another place and has other features. We see that this is an oak tree and not a willow, because we know what oak leaves look like, but each of its leaves has some variation. We see our body, our chest, belly, and arms, and we see a double of our body in the mirror; but the double also has our face which we do not see when we look at our body.

A landscape painting doubles up a landscape. It is not a figment of the imagination. It is real, and, like our reflection in a mirror, we can see things in it that we don't see by just looking at a landscape. Energy, calm or harmony, for example.

When we go to the countryside, into the environment around us, doesn't the question sometimes arise: Does the whole landscape have a double? Is there a world behind the scenes? Like Plato's realm of pure ideas, or, as the Theosophists held, a realm of pure forces or spirits? Symbolist painters depicted scenes that were symbols of this other realm.

Martin Heidegger held that behind or beneath the landscape around us, there is a void, an abyss. We do not see real things, make contact with reality unless we advance toward them, reach for them, manipulate them. And where we reach for food or drink, toxins may lurk; what we manipulate may break or fall and strike us; wherever we walk or stand, the supporting ground may give way. Everywhere we advance, death lurks, the abyss of death opens. The world looks solid and supporting and full of paths and objectives, but we move with anxiety, for at any moment, in the next moment, with the next step, we may fall into the abyss.

Allegro

Let us now look at the first painting – *Allegro*.

Cliffs, cascades, wind-bent trees, blank spaces, in black and grey without color, rocks painted with rough and rapid strokes – are characteristic of Chinese and Japanese painting.

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Allegro (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

There are no people or signs of their passage; the landscape, water and vertical cliffs are remote and inaccessible. Visible only through rough strokes, they elude grasp and measure; the scene is sublime in its desolation.

The visible things in the landscape move the viewer to the right and to the left and above and below, they fragment or multiply the viewer and first the artist. The cliff wall situates the viewer close to it, on the right. The viewer sees it veering off sharply into the distance. There are three equally spaced cascades; the one on the right is closest to the viewer.

The cascades pour into three pools. It is the one on the left that is closest to the viewer. The viewer has now been shifted to a spot on the left, looking up at the three pools.

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Allegro (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. Fragment. 1907. Tempera on paper

Water is transparent, but it reflects objects. They are reflected, duplicated on the surface of the water, and it is the reflection of something outside of it that makes the surface of the water visible.

But in this landscape, the pools themselves are reflected, duplicated on the land.

There is a stretch of flat land at the bottom of the picture; it is closest to us, and situates the viewer in front of it and somewhat above it. There are three ponds on this stretch of land. The three ponds at the base of the cliff wall are reflected, duplicated by the three ponds. There is also a relatively small fourth pond.

On top of the cliff wall there is a blank space that seems to be a river that is pouring over the cliff into the three narrow cascades. In the upper part of the picture there is a land mass with a beach on this side of it that seems to be the other bank of the river. And on the left edge of the picture the river is blocked by land that joins the cliff wall with the land mass on the top of the picture.

But that cannot be. The painting shows the way the cliff wall looks when we are standing on the ground and looking up. Then on top of the cliff wall we

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Allegro (Sonata II)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. Fragment. 1907. Tempera on paper

would see sky. We would see a river only if we are moved up to a height over the river. Then looking down at the cliff wall it would not look like it does here.

On the right there is no line marking the horizon and separating river from sky. What we saw as a river just merges into sky. Perhaps all this blank space over the cliffs is sky.

When we look now at that stretch of land at the top of the picture, we see how big the trees are and we realize we are viewing it from somewhat above it and that it is much closer to us than the cliff wall. It is not on the other side of the river level with the top of the cliff wall; it is instead hovering in the sky and we are viewing it from a position in the sky.

At the bottom of the picture there is a stretch of land with four ponds. The stretch of land in the sky has the same shape and the same four ponds as the stretch of land below; they reflect, duplicate one another.

Let us look at this land mass on top of the picture, the one closest to us. There are trees on it, with sharply drawn outlines and dense black. They are perfectly still.

Four full dense trees alternating with four very slender ones – cedars and cypresses planted in cemeteries. But wait! The top of the land mass is

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Funeral Symphony (VI)*. 1903. Pastel on paper

horizontal, and only the tops of the trees are seen above it. So, this horizontal line on top of this land mass is not the far boundary of this land mass, nor is it the horizon. The trunks and lower branches of the trees are visible in the ponds. Now our vision undergoes a dramatic change! Those are not reflections of the trees on the surface of the water making the surface and making transparent water visible there. Now as we look at that flat stretch of land it turns up on its lower edge and stabilizes as a vertical wall that has four holes in it through which we see the lower branches and trunks of the eight trees. As we look through those holes, our gaze ends at the base of those trees of cemeteries, in the land of death.

The same thing happens in the stretch of land at the bottom of the picture. It too appears and becomes a vertical wall with openings through which we

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Funeral Symphony (IV)*. 1903. Pastel on paper

see the trunks of trees in the land of death. I think that once this happens, we are not going to be able to see it as flat land again.

There are also three such openings in the cliff wall. It is vertical, not a cliff we could climb, instead, it is a wall with openings through which we see the land of death.

However, although there are open holes everywhere in the landscape that Čiurlionis painted, they do not open upon the abyss of nothingness that Heidegger described, and the landscape is not fraught with anxiety. The land of death where the trees grow is a land of rest and life.

Čiurlionis' first paintings, painted in 1903, were a series of seven paintings entitled *Funeral Symphony*. Only the seventh picture is melancholy; a single individual in a desolate room at a window before the night sky. In pictures III and VI, the mourners are together in great numbers, in III bearing the coffin to the setting sun under a golden sky, in VI, to a mountain cave glowing with golden light. In IV, a cemetery in the valley below, seen from behind eight cypress trees, glows with golden light.

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Finale (Sonata IV)*. From cycle *Sonata II (Sonata of the Spring)*. 1907. Tempera on paper

On the top edge of the cliff wall the alternating four full and four slender trees are reflected, doubled, but beaten, bent and torn by the winds. The landscape sounds with silence of the land of death, the howling winds over the cliff wall, the melodious cascades – *Allegro*.

Finale

Here the painting is of space, space beyond the sky.

We are situated in outer space from where planet Earth is seen from a vast distance. Here there is one commanding dominating viewpoint. Two enormous spires, one reflecting the other, rise, held still as the planet whirls by their very broadly splayed bases like the buttress roots of ceiba trees in the American

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Allegro*. From cycle *Sonata VII* (*Sonata of the Pyramids*). 1909. Tempera on paper

tropics. The spires have turrets on top shaped like rosebuds. But the spires are not springtime vegetative growth, they are made of stone. A compact white cloud around one tower reflects, doubles a lake below. They are observation towers, but the turrets have antennae on top and no windows; they are not viewing but listening posts. A thin stream pulls energy spirals around them and is pushed by cosmic winds into the distance, glowing white, rose, turquoise and yellow ochre colors.

The paintings we have examined are unique and do not give us a key to or generalizations about Čiurlionis' work. We noted how the third and the first of this series are painted with characteristics of Far Eastern landscape paintings; these characteristics are not seen in any other paintings by Čiurlionis. *Allegro*

M. K. Čiurlionis. *Allegro*. From cycle *Sonata VII* (*Sonata of the Pyramids*). 1909. Tempera on paper

is the only painting he created with minimal black strokes only and no colors. The doubling and displacement of the viewpoint and viewer, so striking in the first three paintings of *Spring Sonata*, is only found in two other paintings by Čiurlionis, the first two in the *Sonata of the Pyramids*.

Alphonso Lingis

SUVERENUMAS IR PAVALDUMAS
PAVASARIO SONATOJE

Santrauka

M. K. Čiurlionis vadinamas simbolistu, piešiančiu ne gamtos vaizdus, o savo vaizduotės ir svajonių kūrinius. Tačiau keturiuose „Pavasario sonata“ paveikluose jis tiesiog nutapė kalnus, medžius, vėjo malūnus, žuvis ir bokštus. Paveikslai yra vaizduojamieji, o ne abstraktūs. Čiurlionis dažnai detaliai ir tiksliai tapė sudėtingus pastatus ir medžius, tačiau čia tik žuvis forma, kuri turi tik vieną neryškų peleką ir net neturi akių. Šie paveikslai iš tikrųjų vaizduoja ne daiktus. Jie veikiau vaizduoja tai, ką senovės graikai ir filosofas Emmanuelis Levinas vadino elementais. Trečias paveikslas yra apie vandenį. Antrasis – apie dangų, pirmasis – apie atidengtą uolos pamušalą, uolieną ir žemę, susidariusią vandeniui veikiant uolas, o ketvirtasis paveikslas – apie kosminę erdvę. M. K. Čiurlionis tapė ne daiktus, o pirmapradžius elementus – vandenį, dangų, žemę, kosminę erdvę. Jis atskleidžia skirtingus požiūrius ir žavią, malonią patirtį. Jis vaizduoja dalykus, dubliuojančius, atspindinčius vienas kitą ir tai, kas yra už mūsų suvokimo ribų. Kai einame pasimėgauti kraštovaizdžiu, mus vilioja ne tik daiktų formos ir spalvos. Mes patiriame gilesnį susižavėjimą: panyrame į šviesą, į vandenį, į žemės ir uolos substanciją. Žavingas tai, kad tikri dalykai projektuoja savo šešėlius ir atspindžius vandenyje ir miražus ore, jie atsikartoja kituose dalykuose, panašiuose į juos pačius, bet šiek tiek pasikeisdami. Rūpestį kelia ir nerimas, kad kraštovaizdis, kuriame mes gyvename, yra ir mirties šalis.

Raktažodžiai: M. K. Čiurlionis, Pavasario sonata, pirmapradžiai elementai, mirties šalis, estetinė fenomenologija.